

TEACHING ENGLISH INVOLVING MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE

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ABSTRACT

This article explains how important the role of multiple intelligence is in teaching foreign languages to teenagers and adults. Also, based on the discussion of scientists' opinions about the types of multiple intelligence, their features for students are analyzed.

Multiple Intelligences is one of the many learning theories that have attempted to describe how people learn; it has been extensively investigated by educators such as Howard Gardner (1983–1993), Bruce Campbell (1990), Thomas Armstrong (1994), and Mary Ann Christison (2005). Even though there is a wealth of knowledge in this area, there is still much to say and research regarding this topic. Throughout history, numerous learning theories have had an impact on English language teaching, and the Multiple Intelligence Learning theory is no exception. According to several research, teaching EFL and the Multiple Intelligence theory go hand in hand very well since the MI method provides a holistic way of teaching to all types of learners, increasing students' chances of success, understanding, and retention.¹

The Multiple Intelligence theory (The Frames of Mind 1983) is now regarded as a crucial study that has greatly improved teachers' work and students' development both inside and outside of the classroom in real-world situations. This is because the theory aims to assist people in solving any problem they may face throughout their lives. With his theory, Howard Gardner, a professor of education at Harvard University today, challenged the widely held notion of intelligence held by the majority of his contemporaries. According to cognitive views advocate Howard Gardner, intelligence is not just one skill. "The ability to solve problems or to create fashion products that are valued within one or more cultural settings," was how he

¹Gardner, H. (1983). Frames of mind: The theory of multiple intelligence New York: Basic Books.

described intelligence.² He proposed that everyone has a unique mind and that everyone has a unique profile of intellect made up of combinations of eight different intelligence kinds.

Howard Gardner used the following criteria to determine what intelligences are, according to Mary Ann Christison in her book *Multiple Intelligences and Language Learning* :³

1. When someone experiences a brain injury, their IQ is said to be affected, according to studies on brain damage. This does not preclude the individual from utilising the rest of his or her intelligences.
2. This generally means exceptionally intelligent people who identify themselves as prodigies in a certain field.
3. Developmental history. It indicates that each intelligence manifests in a unique manner and at a distinct time in each person.
4. Evolutionary History. Each intelligence has its roots in evolutionary history of man,
5. Psychometric findings. Numerous research results and tests back up the MI theory.
6. Psychological task Psychological research carried separately. A person can not be very good at a logical activity but be excellent at reading.
7. Core operation. Each intelligence has its own main activities or center.
8. Symbol system. Each intelligence can be described as having the potential to exist entirely within one environment.

According to Howard Gardner in Lei, there are eight types of intelligences. They are:

Linguistic Intelligence

This kind of intelligence is concerned with spoken or written language. High linguistic intelligence is demonstrated by a comfort with words and languages. They often excel at reading, writing, storytelling, and memorization of both words and dates⁴. They typically learn best by reading, taking notes, hearing lectures, and participating in discussions and debates. Additionally, they usually possess excellent explanatory, didactic, and oratory or persuasive speaking skills. People with excellent verbal memory and recall skills, as well as the capacity to comprehend and modify syntax and structure, are particularly adept at learning foreign languages.⁵ These intelligences are suited for careers such as writing, law, philosophy, journalism, politics, poetry, and teaching.

Logical-mathematical Intelligence

This theory is concerned with logic, abstraction, justification, and numerical data. Although it's frequently believed that people with this intelligence naturally thrive at arithmetic, chess, computer programming, and other logical or numerical pursuits, a more precise definition of this intelligence focuses emphasis on traditional mathematics skills as well as reasoning abilities, the ability to recognize abstract patterns, scientific thinking and

² Gardner, H. (1999). *Intelligence Reframed: Multiple intelligences for the 21* New York: Basic Books.

³ Hess, N. (2001). *Teaching Large Multilevel Classes* Cambridge Handbooks for Language Teachers/NatalieHess. *Cambridge University Press*, 197, 4.

⁴ Richards, Jack C, *Approaches and Methods in Language Teaching*, (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2001), p. 115.

⁵ Lei, Song, *Applying Multiple Intelligence Theory in Undergraduate EFL Classroom*,(China: Qingdao University, 1999), p. 3.

inquiry, and the capacity for complex calculations⁶. It closely resembles conventional ideas of "intelligence" or IQ. People with high intelligence are well-suited for careers as scientists, mathematicians, engineers, doctors, and economics.

Bodily kinaesthetic Intelligence

In theory, people who have bodily kinaesthetic intelligence should learn better by involving muscular movement such as getting up and moving around into the learning experience, and are generally good at physical activities such as sports or dance. They may enjoy performing or acting, and they typically excel at creating and producing things. Instead of reading or hearing about something, they frequently learn it best by really doing it.⁷ Sportspeople, dancers, musicians, actors, surgeons, doctors, builders, police officers, and soldiers are among the professions that suit those with this intellect.

Musical Intelligence

This intelligence is connected to music, rhythm, and ear jewelry. An increased sensitivity to sounds, rhythms, tones, and music is a sign of high musical-rhythmic intelligence.⁸ They are able to sing, play musical instruments, and write music. They often have good pitch and may even have absolute pitch. People with musical intelligence often have well developed language skills.⁹ People with musical intelligence may also employ music or rhythms to help them learn and remember new material. Instrumentalists, singers, directors, disc jockeys, authors, and composers are among the professions that fit persons with this intelligence.

Spatial-Visual Intelligence

Visualizing things is a component of this intelligence. The senses of form, color, shape, space, and line are sensitive to those who possess spatial intelligence. A good example of spatial intelligence is the capacity to solve spatial problems, such as utilizing a map to find a location in a city or sketching a floor plan.¹⁰ Those with this intelligence are well suited for careers as architects, navigators, painters, sculptors, and graphic artists, among others.

Interpersonal Intelligence

This intelligence relates to social interaction. People with high interpersonal intelligence are typically extroverts who are characterized by their sensitivity to other people's moods, feelings, temperaments, and motives as well as their capacity for teamwork.¹¹ They can be either leaders or followers and communicate emphatically and successfully with others. They frequently like conversation and debate, and they typically learn best when

⁶ Berman, M. (1998). A multiple intelligences road to an ELT classroom. Wales, UK: Crown House Publishing Limited.

⁷ Altan, M. Z. (2012). Introducing the theory of multiple intelligences into English language teaching programs. *Pamukkale University Journal of Education*, 32(2), 57-64.

⁸ Currie, K. L. (2003). Multiple intelligence theory and the ESL classroom--preliminary considerations. *The Internet TESL Journal*, 4(4), 263-270.

⁹ Ibnian, S., & Hadban, A. (2013). Implications of multiple intelligences theory in ELT field. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(4), 292-297.

¹⁰ Nagajothi, N. (2013). Renaissance and Reformation of ELT in India through Multiple Intelligences. *Language in India*, 13(5).

¹¹ Noble, T. (2004). Integrating the revised bloom's taxonomy with multiple Intelligences: A planning tool for curriculum differentiation. *Teachers College Record*, 106(1), 193-211.

collaborating with others.¹² People with this intellect are good at sales, politics, management, teaching, and social work, among other professions.

Intrapersonal Intelligence

This intelligence was concerned with abilities for reflection and introspection. Introverts with intrapersonal intelligence tend to be intuitive and perceptive. They are adept at understanding their own emotions and driving forces. This is a reference to having a thorough grasp of oneself, including knowing your strengths and weaknesses, what makes you special, and whether you can foresee your own reactions or feelings.¹³ People with high intelligence are well suited for careers as philosophers, psychologists, theologians, attorneys, and authors, among others.

Naturalistic Intelligence

This intelligence deals with the natural environment by identifying, classifying, and categorizing the different types of plants, animals, and minerals that can be found there.¹⁴ People with naturalist intelligence can discern which species are good for humans and which are bad for them. Jobs that are suitable for someone with this intellect include geologist, ornithologist, environmentalist, and biologist.¹⁵

The multiple intelligences strategy aims to meet the needs of the students in English language learning according to their intelligences. In this situation, the teacher must be more than just a language instructor; they also need to be facilitators, observers, and lesson planners. The MI approach presents obstacles for teachers in terms of lesson planning, classroom activities, and finding instructional materials.¹⁶

Following Armstrong's explanation, as given by Lash, there are various activities that can assist students in realizing their full potential based on their dominant intelligence:¹⁷

Activities for Linguistic Intelligence

This group of learners takes pleasure in word games, practice exercises, creative writing, and leisure reading. They take pleasure in hearing stories read aloud.

Activities for Logical-Mathematical Intelligence

Chess and checkers are two games they prefer to play for strategy. They are prepared to put in a lot of time solving logic games like the Rubik's cube. They take pleasure in categorizing things and utilizing logic to solve issues.

Activities for Spatial Intelligence

¹² Po-Ying, L. (2006). Multiple intelligences theory and English language teaching. *Retrieved July, 11, 2011.*

¹³ Richards, J. & T. Rodger (2001). *Approaches and methods in language teaching.* Cambridge: Cambridge.

¹⁴ Harmer, Jeremy. 2002. *The Practice of English Language Teaching, Third Edition.* Longman
Lei, Song. 1999. *Applying Multiple Intelligence Theory in Undergraduate EFL Classroom.*
China: Qingdao University.

¹⁵ Elliot, J. 1991. *Action Research for Educational Change.* Philadelphia: Open University Press.

¹⁶ Armstrong, Thomas. 2004. *Multiple Intelligences in the Classroom* 3rd ed. Alexandria, Va: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.

¹⁷ Christison, Mary Ann – Kennedy, Deborah. 2010. *Multiple Intelligences: Multiple Intelligences : Theory and Practice in Adult :* Eric Digest.

One activity that spatially intelligent people could like spending a lot of time doing is art. They like doing crossword puzzles and other visual exercises.

Activities for Bodily-Kinesthetic Intelligence

They excel at intensely competitive sports. To understand something better, they must touch it. These people are skilled at imitating the gestures, mannerisms, and behaviors of others. They enjoy messy activities like working with clay or finger painting.

Activities for Musical Intelligence

This one seems rather obvious. Students that are musically talented like singing, playing instruments, and collecting CDs. They react intensely to many types of music and are sensitive to environmental sounds.

Activities for Interpersonal Intelligence

They like interacting with people in both big and small groups and have a lot of friends. They enjoy playing games with others. They are viewed as natural teachers and teachers themselves.

Activities for Intrapersonal Intelligence

They are aware of their strengths and weaknesses in a realistic manner. They respond angrily when contentious subjects are discussed. They feel confident in themselves.

Activities for Naturalistic Intelligence

Natural environments appeal to people with high naturalist intelligence. They might list camping and hiking as hobbies.

It is boring to teach English using solely the Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and a lecture-style or approach. It must be altered to the application of multiple intelligence consideration, which is roughly in line with Intelligence Quotient (IQ), which assesses a limited set of verbal/linguistics and logical/mathematical abilities, and Emotional Intelligence. The MI theory increases language teachers' awareness of the variety of potentials in a language learning classroom and the many ways pupils learn. This has an impact on how they instruct. The procedure does not impair the learner's capacity, which is a good input, and this is the most compelling argument. Teachers get a stronger regard for students' skills and a deeper understanding of their learning preferences.;

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